

CONCEPT AS A BASIC NOTION OF COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: As is known that linguistics and variety fields of it were developed in every period of developing process. Hence, we can observe that in the XVIII century, research carried out in comparative-historical aspect among cognate languages and in the last century collection of anthropocentric, functional, cognitive and dynamic paradigms occupied the position of structural paradigm. Change of researcher's interests from the object of cognition to the subject of anthropocentric paradigm, in other words, to the analysis of language from anthropological point of view is a demand of time. List of areas are developing in the anthropocentric paradigm of the modern linguistics and cognitive linguistics and linguaculturology are considered the urgent directions of it. Cognitive linguistics investigates language as mechanism of transformation and codification of it. The aim of this linguistics covers the cognition of the world from ones point of view and ways of appearing of receiving processes, categorization, and classification of it.

Keywords: cognition, cognitive linguistics, concept, conceptual world picture, cultural concept., linguaculturology, paradigm, process, mind

Introduction: Linguaculturology is a complex scientific science direction appeared in the basis of inter reaction of linguistics and culturology. This direction investigates interconnection between culture and language, and researches the language as a phenomenon of culture. It shows the observation of the world in the certain view by the cultural prism and by a certain nation's mind and culture. Change of researcher's interests from the object of cognition to the subject of anthropocentric paradigm, in other words, to the analysis of language from anthropological point of view is a demand of time. List of areas are developing in the anthropocentric paradigm of the modern linguistics and cognitive linguistics and linguaculturology are considered the urgent directions of it. Cognitive linguistics investigates language as mechanism of transformation and codification of it. The aim of this linguistics covers the cognition of the world from ones point of view and ways of appearing of receiving processes, categorization, and classification of it.

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According to a number of specialists, cognitive linguistics and linguaculturology are progressing in the frame of the collection of single general cognitive sciences(1, 37–47). The term of “Cognitive science” includes learning processes jointly, receiving them and reworking, saving and using, organizing structure of knowledge and collection, furthermore, it arranges collection of a certain scientific thoughts which is joint for forming the mental activity of these structures. Cognitive science is closely connected with mathematics, logic, philosophy, anthropology and linguistics.

Thus, dyad of “Language and human being” is inherent to the two above-mentioned directions of the anthropocentric paradigm. Moreover, terms of “concept” and “world picture” have a peculiar notion and importance in these directions of linguistics.

In cognitive linguistics there is understood with the means of concept all world pictures reflected in operative multiple unit of the memory, mental lexicon, conceptual systems and mental language and notion of human being. From the point of view of cognitive linguistics, concepts are embodied in the brain, and they are complex units that are appeared in the intellect of human being in the process of thinking. With another words, concepts can be seen as units where can be saved knowledge of human being. In cognitive linguistics, concepts are the units of conceptalsystems, which include the information about world and interpreted by language expressions (2, 83–90). Thus, in cognitive linguistics the dyad of “language and human being” changes into the triad “language-human being-mind”. Conceptual researches have an important role as well in linguaculturology as cognitive linguistics. Cultural concept is considered as a subject of research of linguaculturology, when the subject of the research of cognitive linguistics is cognitive concept. In linguaculturology concept can be understood as “cultural-mental-lexical” expression. Cultural concept is considered as multifunctional mental expression. According to the opinion of Yu. S. Stepanov concept is a part of the culture in the mind of human being and with this, he includes the culture into the mental world of human being (3, 40–76). The dyad of “language and human being”

of anthropocentric paradigm changes into the construction of “language-human being-culture” in linguaculturology. The task of differentiating the cognitive concept from cultural concept is becoming important issue. Some scientists differentiate them in a different ways. G.G. Slyshkyn expresses these distinctions as follows:

- 1) due to cognitivists one concept is equal to one verbal unit. Linguoculturologists consider that one concept can be expressed by several language units.
- 2) as for cognitivists each word has its own concepts. Nevertheless, linguoculturologists think that the basis of the concept is consists of certain cultural units(4, 8, 22).

According to Babaeva the basis of cultural concept is tradition (5, 110–111). M Thus, the feature of expressing tradition differentiates cultural concept from cognitive concept. Furthermore, there can be said that the task of cognitive linguistics is to identify the types concepts, and the research of linguistic culturology is to create conceptual dictionaries enriched with notions of cultures and traditions. It is important to point that in the basis of cognitive linguistics and linguaculturology a number of directions are developing. For instance, in the recent ten years of the last century based on cognitive linguistics and policy science political linguistics is appeared which studies the complex communication units of discourse. Together with this in linguaculturology also developed axiological linguistics which investigates the mores with philosophical naming.

Nowadays, cognitive approach, concept and conceptualization have become traditional, and in the context of its priorities, the language has not already considered as something that exists “in itself and for itself”. Today, the term “concept” has gained great popularity in science. The image of concept is as bipartite unity of knowledge, on the one hand is facing the language, the other hand is to the mental world of man (6). Considering the concepts “a bunch of culture in human consciousness”, the researchers N.D.Arutiunova, Y.S.Stepanov, A.D.Shmelev, E.S.Yakovlev show the basic concepts that exists in each and actual for every person, however, they are not only universal, but also are nationally specific.

In spite of the fact that the present state of linguoculturology research is characterized by a lack of general methodological foundations and common conceptual approaches; additionally there is no clear theoretical basis, commonly accepted terminology, fundamental assumptions, which would allow representatives of different directions and trends achieve mutual understanding.

As a conclusion, it can be said that there was done a brief analysis of differentiating the notions of “concept” and “world picture” in cognitive linguistics and linguaculturology. As the result of the analysis, it can be shown as general similarity of usage of the same terms in both cognitive linguistics and linguaculturology, integrative approach to the language, the main attention which is paid to the dyad of “language and human” in investigating concept and world picture. In the other hand, usage and expressing of these concepts in their own limits and in certain conceptual and cultural frames can be observed. The concept codified in the consciousness both by a notion and an individual sensual image. Depending on the level of understanding of these essences, the conceptual focus can be manifested by notion or a basic idea which are based on the most stable central substantial components that cover the main essence of the concept content.

The theory and description of concepts must separate the contents and the structure of a concept. The concept structure includes the basic structural components of various cognitive nature which form the concept – the sensual image, the informational and interpretational fields.

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